

DyMoN Data Hub, tools and data processing model

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Administrative Information

Basic information on the DyMoN project and the present deliverable:

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Purpose of the document

This document describes the necessary procedures to conceptually design and technically implement the DyMoN framework. It is an outcome of the WP 3, the objectives of which are the following: definition of project's information demand; translation of information demand to data demand; development of the data processing model of the Data Hub; data acquisition and storage in the Data Hub; development of nudge ontologies; design of the DyMoN API that provides the services of the DyMoN framework to the end-clients. This deliverable is related to the tasks in the following working packages. Nudging ontologies are developed based on the context of nudges designed in WP 2, while the implementation of the DyMoN framework is the part of the field study in Salzburg within WP 4.

Executive Summary

The purpose of this document is to describe the Data Hub with its data processing model, software architecture and clients, and potential uses for situation-aware nudging. The content consists of the following parts:

Nudge ontologies

- Situation awareness and its role in nudging approaches
- Rulesets translating the text representation of situation in nudges into data thresholds and conditional statements

Data processing model

- Data processing model of the data hub defining the steps necessary to acquire and prepare data from its raw state to final information stored in the data hub.
- Data assessment matrix that identifies data availability and suitability according to information demand for the nudging repository, dashboard, and simulation model.
- Data acquisition requirements
- Syntactic interoperability of data that identifies how to join different datasets to generate information

Software architecture

- Technical specifications of the Data Hub with its data and nudge repositories, and its API that provides calculated data layers and nudges to the DyMoN API.
- Technical specification of the DyMoN API that provides data layers and nudges to external end-clients, such as the citizens' app and dashboard

End-clients

- Functional requirements of the citizens' app in order to adopt DyMoN framework's services
- Design of the dashboard for city managers and citizens to monitor mobility-related data and assist in decision-making

Glossary

Citizens' mobile application is an application whose purpose is to promote sustainable mobility to citizens via sending digital situation-aware nudges according to their preferences and real-time environmental conditions.

Dashboard is a web-based visualization platform that demonstrates mobility-related data to monitor changes in behaviour and environment and assist in decision-making. The target group can be city managers and citizens.

Data Hub is a data warehouse that stores data and nudges from different sources in a harmonized and structured way. It consists of data repository and nudging repository. Its API provides secure access to its content for the DyMoN API. Calculations of data layers for a dashboard and nudges for a citizens' application is done within the Data Hub.

Data repository is the part of the Data Hub, where data for the dashboard and nudge calculation is stored.

DyMoN framework is an application framework consisting of the Data Hub and the DyMoN API that provides nudging functionality for adoption by external applications.

End client is an external application that uses the services of the DyMoN framework by accessing data layers and personalized situation-aware nudges. End-clients can be a city managers' dashboard or a citizens' mobile application.

DyMoN API is a middle point between the Data Hub and external applications that schedules nudges and provides secure communication.

Nudging repository is the part of the Data Hub where nudges with their textual content and situational thresholds are stored.

1 Introduction

The promotion of sustainable mobility is central for tackling negative effects of motorized individual transport. While the emission of greenhouse gases (GHG) could have been reduced in almost all relevant sectors, the level of emissions does not decline in the transport sector. According to latest numbers by the Austrian Federal Environment Agency, CO₂ emissions from transport increased by 74.4% between 1990 and 2019, while all other sectors saw substantial reductions. Thus, it is essential to stimulate and support the shift to sustainable modes through comprehensive, concerted interventions. Gössling (2020) identified three elements, which are essential for the required shift. We summarize and partly extend these elements as:

- a) **Viable alternatives** to car-centred mobility, with high quality public transport as backbone as well as a good mix of functions in close proximity and high accessibility of facilities for daily purposes (“15-minutes city”)
- b) **Adequate** – that is safe and comfortable – **infrastructure** for pedestrians and cyclists
- c) **Communication** strategies that frame non-car transport positively, adapts socio-cultural norms and account for non-rationality in mobility choices

The first two aspects address external (environmental) determinants of mode choice. Here, we distinguish between

- the built environment and its organization: road design, urban morphology, accessibility, connectivity, level of service etc.
- the natural environment: topography, exposure to green and blue space etc.
- dynamic environmental factors: precipitation, wind, temperature, road conditions, seasonal variations, exposure to pollutants or noise etc.
- dynamic system variables: velocity of traffic, occupancy rate in public transport

In almost every strategic paper, these factors and their importance for mobility behaviour is anticipated. Factors that are adaptable, such as the provision of adequate infrastructure for pedestrians and cyclists, are core to sustainable urban mobility plans (SUMP) and planning documents. However, the third aspect remains often omitted. Although mounting evidence proves that mobility behaviour cannot be explained and adapted by economic arguments (rational choices based on complete knowledge), research on how sustainable mobility can be boosted by behavioural interventions remains scarce. Likewise, the number of implemented policies and successful campaigns is limited. Due to the habitual character of mobility behaviour, and potentially biased choices, purely rational approaches, such as information provision, have been proven to be of little effectivity. Thus, internal (personal) factors, such as norms, values, attitudes, and preferences need to be considered, if the turnaround in the transport sector is actually to be achieved.

In any comprehensive promotion of sustainable mobility, external and internal determinants for mode choice need to be addressed. In DyMoN, external factors – that is the representation of the four types of environmental and system variables listed before – are represented in a geographical information system (GIS). Time and location are used as primary keys for not integrating various data and information layers, but also relating individuals with their immediate environment. Nudging in context of the DyMoN project aims at influencing and modifying mobility behaviour by addressing internal factors for mode choice. Situation-aware nudges consider both, internal and external determinants for mode choice.

In this deliverable document, we describe the DyMoN framework, which is designed for the purpose of nudging end users towards sustainable mobility and to provide relevant information in an easily accessible way. In the DyMoN framework, all strands of this research project come together conceptually and technically: the extensive set of nudges, data from various sources and of different form, as well as the interfaces for end clients, namely a dashboard for information visualization and a citizen app for delivering situation-aware nudges.

2 Nudge ontologies

Models in traditional economy assume rational decisions by all actors (“*homo oeconomicus*”). In contrast to this assumption, behavioural economics works with the heuristics of human behaviour and considers cognitive biases in judgements and decisions. Nudging, as an increasingly popular sub-domain of behavioural economics, focuses on the choice architecture. By slight adoptions of the choice architecture and without changing the economic parameters (incentives or penalties) or neglecting options, addressees of nudges are steered into predictable directions. Driven by the digital transformation – with the smartphone and ubiquitous internet access as immediate manifestation in everyone’s everyday life – an increasing number of choices are made in a digital environment. Consequently, digital nudging opened new opportunities for modifying human behaviour. Weinmann et al. (2016) define digital nudging as “the use of user-interface design elements to guide people’s behaviour (sic.) in digital choice environments.”

The number of digital nudging applications in the context of sustainable mobility that are described and evaluated scientifically is rather low. Santos Silva (2022) provides a useful review of practical, legal, and ethical aspects of “green nudges”, but without touching the transport sector specifically. Casquero et al. (2022) investigated the effectivity of mobility applications in stimulating mode switches from car to public transport. They showed moderate effects when useful functionalities, such as door-to-door ticketing or real time arrival and departure information, are combined with pervasive elements, such as gamification, social comparison, or challenges. In an extensive review report for the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (Mont et al., 2014), the authors point to the fact the success in terms of efficiency and effectivity of nudges is ultimately dependent from framework conditions. This means, for instance, that nudging towards sustainable modes can only be successful if the provided infrastructure and level of service are adequate and attractive, which is in line with the three fundamental elements for mode shift identified by Gössling (2020).

2.1 Situation awareness

The concept of situation aware nudging, which is at the core of the DyMoN project, draws from the findings that a) the built, natural, and socio-cultural environment has an effect on mobility choices and b) internal or personal decisions are not made entirely rational. Situation aware nudging considers both classes of determinants for mobility behaviour and are thus regarded as promising in terms of efficiency and effectivity.

GIScience and Human-Computer-Interaction are two domains that provide the conceptual foundation for the definition of “situations” and are thus key for designing situation-aware nudges. In both fields context- or situation-awareness plays a central role:

- All methods and tools from GIScience ultimately depend on the spatial reference and the spatial characteristics of data (“everything happens somewhere”). In particular, location-based-services (LBS), are conceptually relevant for situation-awareness. The miniaturization of sensors, the widespread use of mobile devices and ubiquitous internet access paved the way for LBS in research and application. It is no coincidence that the location function is a basic requirement for many apps on the smartphone.
- In Human-Computer-Interaction (HCI), context is a fundamental parameter, since the user as well as the system depends on the conditions in which interaction happens. In this sense, context is not understood as a static entity, but as part of a process. Designing the context and adapting to variables is central for the usability and subsequently for the success of systems.

In our case, digital nudges are conveyed to users, who receive them in specific situations. Hence, we need to represent the context or situation of the user digitally and link the user to this digital sphere. In doing so, concepts from GIScience and HCI are helpful for capturing and adapting the choice architecture of individual users.

In her seminal paper “Context is Key”, Joëlle Coutaz and colleagues (Coutaz et al., 2005) define context as an information space. We adopt this understanding for the purpose of DyMoN and represent this information space on four different levels, following Coutaz et al. (2005):

- a) **Data:** multiple real-time sensors and data sources, which represent environmental variables, are integrated in a comprehensive data architecture
- b) **Information:** situations are described along external determinants, such as access to adequate infrastructure or weather, for mobility choices
- c) **Situation identification:** an ontology translates definitions of situations (“nice weather”, “good bikeability”) into manageable framework conditions
- d) **Trigger for nudges:** situation-aware nudges are delivered to users following pre-defined rules, which are either drawn from the semantic content of the nudge itself, or from conditional variables

We use the spatial and temporal reference as keys for the definition of situation and for linking this representation of a situation with individual users, who receive nudges. With this, we can design a set of nudges that either contain semantic information about a situation (“Next to your home location is a bus stop and the weather is going to be wet. Take the bus today!”) or are tied to situational conditions (“Why not enjoy the fresh air and walk to work today?” – conditions: user is still at home and low emission level and good walkability around current location).

Technically, the four levels of abstraction, listed above, build on each other. Data are stored and managed in a spatial database, which forms the building block of the DyMoN data hub. Levels b-d are reflected in how the data are queried.

2.2 Rulesets

2.2.1 Nudge attributes

Nudges are characterized by several attributes that define their suitability for each user. They are listed in Table 1. Nudging repository consists of nudges that can be categorized by mode, correspondence to proof-of-concept study and definition of situation awareness. Each nudge

is designed for specific mode, such as walking, bicycling, and public transport. For example, a nudge that is aimed to promote bicycling follows as: “It is a beautiful day to bicycle to work today!”. Some nudges due to the possible functionality limitations of an end-client application cannot be implemented in the field study for the proof-of-concept and specified as such.

The situation awareness can be attributed to two types of situation-aware nudges. Some nudges have a semantic representation of a situation in a text: “Lots of traffic going on - why don't you use your bicycle today?”. The situation described points out at traffic in the proximity of a user at a specific point in time, and the nudge suggests using a bicycle. Another example does not include semantical representation of a situation: “Remember to ride your bicycle today!”. Despite the absence of the situation description, certain conditions must be in place for a nudge to be sent. This nudge is proposed to a user if environmental conditions are satisfactory for bicycling, meaning the weather is not rainy, no strong winds and glaze, user's destination is in bicycling proximity and there is good infrastructure along a route. Non-situation-aware nudges are also without semantic representation of a situation in their text, however specific environmental pre-conditions by mode are not considered. In that case, the same nudge “Remember to ride your bicycle today!” can be sent to all users irrelevantly of weather and infrastructure quality.

Since one of the project purposes is to define how effective situation-aware nudges are against non-situation-aware nudges, there are two groups of users in the field study: control and intervention groups. Control group receive non-situation-aware nudges, while intervention group receives situation-aware nudges.

Table 1 Nudge attributes and possible values

Attribute name	Description	Possible values
nudge_id	unique identifier	
nudge_title	short title of a nudge notification	
nudge_text	nudge notification message in german	
nudge_text_eng	nudge notification message in english	
mode	target transport mode	walking bicycling public
user_group	type of user group in a test study	Intervention, control
timeframe_for_nudge	scheduled time thresholds	morning midday evening before work Friday afternoon anytime after activity at the end of each day (when activity was recorded)

		one week after goal setting (behaviour) Sunday
weekdays	scheduled day of week	Monday, Tuesday...Sunday
time_start	scheduled start time	hh:mm:ss
time_end	scheduled end time	hh:mm:ss
location_start	assumed starting point for situation assessment	home current work
location_end	assumed destination point for situation assessment	home current work
situational_factors	situation description via spatio- temporal conditions of an environment	
temporal_filter	timeframe of situation (forecast for current day/next day)	current day next day
temperature	temperature type	moderate positive
precipitation	presence of rainfall	rainfall no rainfall
precipitation_window	presence of rainfall at a specific period	no rainfall next hour
glaze	presence of glaze	no glaze
wind	presence of wind	no strong winds
sunshine	presence of sunshine	sunshine
walkability	quality of network regarding pedestrian comfort and safety	high
bikeability	quality of network regarding cyclist comfort and safety	high
trip_distance	distance to destination by mode	reasonable
pt_proximity	presence of public transport stop	present
pt_departure_frequency	frequency of departures per 15 min at transport stops	high
pt_occupancy	occupancy rate in % at transport stops	low
bicycle_infrastructure	presence of bicycle parking	present

traffic_state	traffic state	congested
car_parking_availability	car parking availability in %	low
green_bicycle_way	presence of areas with green spaces, like parks and forests along a bicycle way	present
green_walkway	presence of areas with green spaces, like parks and forests along a walkway	present
beautiful_walkway	presence of walkways with green and water spaces around	present
safe_bicycle_way	presence of safe bicycle ways	present

2.2.2 Rulesets

The calculation of nudges is user-centric and requires some information of a user:

- intervention/control group
- mode preference
- time of request
- current location
- home/work locations
- nudge_ids

Figure 1 shows the general workflow of a ruleset. According to this workflow, once user information is received in a nudge request, the algorithm in the Data Hub selects nudges accordingly based on several attributes: user group, mode, timeframe, and situational factors. Situational factors are considered only if the user group is “intervention”. A request’s time and user’s current, home, and work locations are needed to calculate user’s situational context and compare it with the thresholds for situational factors. Next, the algorithm uses the last information in “nudge_ids” which corresponds to nudges that were already sent to a specific user within the last days. To avoid a repetition of a nudge sent per user, they are excluded by the algorithm. The nudges that have been sent to a user are stored and reset every Monday 01:00 o’clock and Friday 01:00 o’clock. As a result, the same nudge cannot be sent from Monday to Thursday and from Friday to Sunday. At last, a random nudge is selected from the list of resulted suitable nudges.

Figure 1 General workflow of a nudge ruleset

Assumptions are required to translate timeframes of sending nudges into specific start/end times and weekdays. These assumptions are presented in the Table 2.

Table 2 Timeframe assumptions

Timeframe	Weekday start	Weekday end	Time start	Time end
morning	Monday	Friday	06:00	08:00
Tuesday morning	Tuesday	Tuesday	06:00	08:00
midday	Monday	Friday or Sunday	12:00	14:00
Friday afternoon	Friday	Friday	12:00	18:00
evening before work	Sunday	Thursday	18:00	22:00
at the end of each day	Monday	Sunday	18:00	22:00
anytime	Monday	Friday or Sunday	06:00 18:00	08:00 22:00
after activity	Monday	Sunday	06:00 18:00	08:00 22:00
one week after goal setting	Monday	Sunday	06:00 18:00	08:00 22:00
Sunday	Sunday	Sunday	06:00 18:00	08:00 22:00

2.2.3 Situational factors and thresholds

Situational factors can describe environment around a user at a specific moment in time from temporal and spatial perspectives:

Spatial perspective. Factors, such as walkability, bikeability, trip distance, public transport stops in proximity, etc. are static from temporal perspective, as changes occur slowly, or temporal aspect is irrelevant.

Spatio-temporal perspective. There are factors that change their state in space and time in relation to a user: weather factors, air pollution, traffic state, congestions, and occupancy of public transport.

Each nudge includes different groups of factors. Figure 2 demonstrates the different parts of situational context. There are some factors regarding spatial characteristics of a trip that must be fulfilled according to proposed mode of transport. For nudges to walk, the walkability and reachable walking distance to a destination is always considered. For nudges to bicycle, the bikeability and reachable bicycling distance are important. For public transport, these factors are the presence of stops in proximity and frequency of departures. Weather factors vary between moderate, excellent, bad, or not specified. The last group of factors is unique to each nudge. These factors can be specified or not depending on a nudge text: air pollution, traffic state, car parking occupancy, etc.

Figure 2 Situational context example

Thresholds for each situational factor in a ruleset are presented in Table 3. In this table values represent possible values identified for the nudging repository. Thresholds are given for bicycle, walk, and public transport modes.

Table 3 Situational factors and thresholds for bicycle, walk, and public transport modes

Situational factor	Value	Threshold	Bicycle	Walk	PT
temperature	moderate	min/max daily mean temperature	-5 - 25 C°	-15 - 20 C°	

	positive	>= daily mean temperature			
precipitation	rainfall	> daily mean precipitation	0.0 mm/h	0.0 mm/h	0.0 mm/h
	no rainfall	= daily mean precipitation	0.0 mm/h	0.0 mm/h	0.0 mm/h
precipitation window	no rainfall next hour	= daily mean precipitation	0.0 mm/h	0.0 mm/h	0.0 mm/h
glaze	no glaze	> daily mean temperature	0 C°		
		or = daily mean precipitation	0.0 mm/h		
wind	no strong winds	< daily mean wind speed	11 m/s	11 m/s	11 m/s
sunshine	sunshine	>= daily sunshine duration	4 h	4 h	4 h
walkability	high	<= mean walkability		0.5	
bikeability	high	<= mean bikeability	0.5		
trip distance	reasonable	<= distance	10000 m	4000 m	
public transport stops in proximity	present	>= number of public transport stops			1
departure frequency at public transport stop	high	>= daily mean of departure frequency interval			10 min
occupancy of public transport	low	<= daily mean of occupancy rate			50 %
traffic state	congested	= traffic state	congested	congested	congested
car parking availability	low	<= parking availability	20 %	20 %	20 %
green bicycle way	present	<= mean green bicycle way index	0.5		
green walkway	present	<= mean green walkway index		0.5	
beautiful walkway	present	>= mean beautiful walkway index		0.5	
safe bicycle way	present	>= mean safe bicycle way index	0.5		

Thresholds' definition is carried out according to common knowledge and several sources specified in Table 4.

Table 4 Input data for definition of situational factor thresholds

Situational factor	Source
precipitation	Precipitation intensity scale (Deutscher Wetterdienst, 2022)

wind	Beaufort wind speed scale (Met Office, 2022)
trip distance	Mobilitätserhebung Land Salzburg (Federal State of Salzburg, Transport Department, 2012)
public transport stops in proximity	ÖV-Güteklassen (Team Datenanalyse und Modelle (AustriaTech), 2022)
departure frequency at public transport stop	ÖV-Güteklassen (Team Datenanalyse und Modelle (AustriaTech), 2022)

Some situational factors are calculated along a route or in proximity depending on locational information. If a destination point is known, usually in case of a trip to work, a route can be calculated between current/home location and destination location. Then, route's mean walkability index is compared with the threshold given in the Table 3. If a destination point is unknown, mean walkability index is calculated for the area around a current/home location. The radius for proximity is identified for each situational factor between 200-500 m.

If measurements and values for most factors are gathered from acquired dataset, several situational factors, such as walkability, bikeability, green area, beautiful walkway, and safe bicycle way require more comprehensive calculations. They follow the approach of the network assessment with walkability and bikeability indices developed by Z_GIS at University of Salzburg (<https://github.com/plus-mobilitylab/netascore>). Walkability is an attribute that represents various aspects for comfortable walking, such as pedestrian infrastructure, number of crossings, pleasant green and water areas, heterogeneous facilities, etc. Bikeability reflects indicators important for safe and pleasant bicycling, such as the quality of bicycle infrastructure, slope gradient, road category, maximum speed, etc. To use this assessment approach to estimate beautiful walkways and safe bicycle ways, respective indicators are weighted higher accordingly: green ratio, water ratio, max speed, road category, etc.

3 Data Processing Model

Extensive data is required for the project purposes. All acquired data are stored in the Data Hub. Data preparation and analysis includes several processes visualized in the data processing model of the Data Hub in Figure 3.

- **Extraction:** raw data are extracted from various sources
- **Harmonization:** data are harmonized by data format, geometry type, spatial reference system; syntactic and topological errors are checked and corrected
- **Preparation analysis:** generic datasets are calculated for further use and calculations
- **Integration:** generic datasets are stored in the data repository of the Data Hub
- **Analysis:** nudges and data layers are calculated dynamically per web-request
- **Trigger analysis:** calculation of nudges and data layers is triggered
- **Sharing:** nudges and data layers are shared with the DyMoN API

Figure 3 Data processing model

Processes, such as extraction, harmonization, preparation analysis, and integration are happening dynamically throughout the project time span, as new data are incoming. They prepare datasets for further calculation of nudges and data layers. Processes, such as analysis, trigger analysis, and sharing occur when web-requests are received from the DyMoN API. These processes calculate nudges and data layers and sent them back to the DyMoN API.

3.1 Information demand to data demand

Data demand depends on the information demand that is defined during the conceptual design of the nudging repository and simulation model, as well as through the expert interviews about the dashboard. The data assessment matrix was prepared to collect all information demand, define its purpose and importance for the project, define potential datasets that would satisfy the demand, and estimate its applicability for the project. The aim of the data assessment matrix is to ensure efficient data acquisition, provide maximum transparency and opportunity to trace all the use-cases back to their data sources. It also showcases the actual feasibility of conceptually designed development processes that is restricted to data availability.

The matrix consists of 4 groups of attributes that must be defined per each information demand and corresponding data: information demand, project aims, data, and relevance (Table 5). Information demand category describes information required for the project purposes in terms of its technical composition. Project aims category identifies how information is related to project’s objectives. Data category describes potential datasets that are suitable from the technical aspect, including the costs of acquisition, licencing, and data governance. The last group is relevance of both information demand and potential datasets in terms of its availability, importance regarding project aims, suitability, acquisition effort, and applicability index.

Table 5 Content of the data assessment matrix

Attribute	Description
Information demand	
Information	Information required for the project
Type of measurement	Temporal aspect of measurement (historical, real-time, forecast)
Temporal extent	Data collection period (real-time/historical data)

Spatial extent	Data collection area
Temporal resolution	Time interval between two measurements
Spatial resolution/geometry type	Area of a single measurement (polygon) or geometry type (point, line)
Measurement unit	Measurement unit
Project aims	
Purpose	Purpose defined by the project
Outcome	Project-specific objectives
Aspect	Keyword for a phenomenon being described
Data	
Dataset	Dataset or combination of datasets for information retrieval
Type	Primary or derived information
Type of measurement	Temporal aspect of measurement (historical, real-time, forecast)
Composition	Data description and attributes
Temporal resolution	Time interval between two measurements
Spatial resolution/geometry type	Area of a single measurement (polygon) or geometry type (point, line)
Update frequency	Time interval between data updates
Sensitivity	Ethical considerations and access/distribution restrictions
Source	Data provider/maintainer
Cost	Monetary cost
Data Governance	Availability of information on how to access data, find contact person, prepare contract, and licence agreements
Data sharing service	Method of data transaction from a source to a client, such as web services, API, FTP, cloud-based sharing, peer-to-peer networks, etc.
Documentation	General description of data, metadata, attributes, procedures of data extraction and manipulation
Relevance	
Availability	Availability status of data
Importance	The importance of the presence/absence of information in terms of project aims
Suitability	Suitability of a dataset based on reliability and its matching characteristics with information demand, such as measurement type, composition, temporal and spatial resolutions, and update frequency

Acquisition effort	Effort to acquire data based on a monetary cost, data sharing services, documentation, and data governance (finding contact persons, preparing contract and licence agreements)
Applicability index	Final assessment rate of data relevance

The relevance attributes are rated according to the classification scale presented in Table 6 and are used to calculate the final applicability index following the equation below:

$$\text{Index} = \text{Availability} * (3 \text{ Importance} * 2 \text{ Suitability} * \text{Acquisition effort})$$

The index values range between 0 to 30, with maximum value meaning that the specified data are available, highly suitable, and important for the project aims, and is easy in acquisition. The results of the assessment matrix are given in Table 7.

Table 6 Classification scale of relevance attributes

Attribute	Classification scale
Availability	1 "available" 0 "unavailable"
Importance	1 "very low" - "nice to have" information that extends the purpose of a project 2 "low" - low priority information, when the core purpose of a project can still be met in its absence 3 "moderate" - noteworthy information that allows approximations 4 "high" - high priority information that significantly benefit the purpose of a project 5 "very high" - top priority information, vital for the purpose of a project
Suitability	1 "very low" – poorly fitting dataset 2 "low" - dataset with a few significant discrepancies 3 "medium" – satisfactory fit of a dataset with a few mismatches that could be replaced by aggregated or imitated estimates 4 "high" – a sufficiently fitting dataset with only a minor discrepancy 5 "very high" – perfectly suitable dataset
Acquisition effort	1 "very high" – data acquisition requires great effort to access proprietary data due to ambiguous information on procedures for contracting, licencing, data transfer and data manipulation. 2 "high" – burdensome effort to access a dataset with a few significant obstacles (3 out of 4) 3 "medium" – challenging to acquire due to a few obstacles (2 out of 4) 4 "low" – well-documented and accessible dataset, however, requires minor effort (1 out of 4) 5 "very low" – effortless to acquire, a dataset is freely available via standard transfer procedures, documentation is provided

Table 7 Results of the data assessment matrix

Information	Av	I	S	Ac	Ind
Weather					
Rainfall forecast	1	5	5	4	29
Temperature real-time/forecast	1	5	5	4	29
Glaze real-time/forecast	1	5	5	4	29
Wind real-time/forecast	1	5	5	4	29
Sunshine real-time/forecast	1	5	5	4	29
Environmental information					
Temperature real-time at test area	1	5	5	4	29
Noise real-time at test area	1	4	5	4	26
Air quality forecast	1	3	5	4	23
Noise historical	1	3	4	5	22
Trip planning					
Public transport scheduling and routing	1	5	5	4	29
Individual routing advice	0	3	0	0	0
Infrastructure					
Public transport stops and departure frequency	1	5	5	5	30
Bicycle infrastructure with temporal construction sites	1	5	5	5	30
Bikeability network	1	5	5	5	30
Walkability network	1	5	5	5	30
Beautiful walkways	1	5	5	5	30
Safe bicycle lanes	1	5	5	5	30
Green spaces	1	5	5	5	30
Parking slots/spaces for bicycles	1	4	5	5	27
Charging stations for e-bikes	1	3	5	5	24
Occupation of car parking facilities	1	3	5	4	23
Bike sharing stations	1	2	5	5	21
Occupation of bicycle parking facilities	0	1	0	0	0
Mobility					

Trip distances	1	5	5	5	30
Travel survey	1	2	5	5	21
Traffic					
Congestion, troubles, construction sites, and events	1	5	5	4	29
Passenger occupancy in public transport	1	5	5	3	28
Floating car data	1	4	5	3	25
Bicycle traffic volume at stations	1	3	5	5	24
Motorized traffic forecast	1	2	5	3	19
Motorized traffic at stations	1	2	5	3	19
Origin-Destination-data	1	1	4	5	16
Floating bicycle data	1	2	3	4	16
User information					
Socio-demographic	1	5	5	1	26
Trip purpose	0	5	0	0	0
Mode of transport	0	4	0	0	0
GPS	0	1	0	0	0
GSM	0	1	0	0	0

* Av – availability, I – importance, S – suitability, Ac – acquisition effort, Ind – applicability index

3.2 Data acquisition

Based on the information and the derived data demand, the respective data must be acquired. Many authors in the academic literature tend to have an optimistic perspective on data availability in urban studies and mobility research. Kitchin (2014) summarizes the current discussion like this, “The hype and hope of big data is a transformation in the knowledge and governance of cities through the creation of a data deluge that seeks to provide much more sophisticated, wider-scale, finer-grained, real-time understanding and control of urbanity”. Anda et al. (2017) as well as Miller and Shaw (2015) describe new opportunities for transport modelling and transport geography respectively that are boosted by emerging data sources (tracking apps, mobile phone data, smart card data etc.). Although it is beyond any doubt that the increase of connected sensors and (mobile) devices has led to unprecedented amounts of data, we have to be careful about specific cases. First of all, it has to be noted that data availability is different from data accessibility. In a recent study, the author challenged the promises of data availability and accessibility in European smart cities and showed that the reality is way less shiny than often proclaimed (Loidl, 2021). The main concerns with regard to data that are suitable for adequately describing situations as outlined in section 2.1 are:

- **Data accessibility:** Data might exist but are not accessible for the general public or even not for research purposes. This holds true for proprietary data, which are either used for private business or are classified as sensitive, and partly for governmental data. The latter is currently partly changing due to the growing pressure towards Open Government Data policies.
- **Metadata:** Data are always generated for a specific (primary) purpose. In order to make data reusable (secondary data use), a valid description of the data (metadata) is ultimately required. Although metadata standards exist, many data are still poorly described and thus of little use for further applications.
- **Data quality and fitness for purpose:** Tightly connected to the lack of metadata, quality issues and the fitness for purpose are the main barriers for secondary data use. As long as no information on accuracy, validity, sampling intervals, spatial and temporal resolution, or attributive consistency is available, data can hardly be used without risking severe biases.
- **Lack of data:** Despite the huge amount of data that is generated, useful data might not be existing in some cases. This holds particularly true for local, timely data on non-motorized traffic, such as the number of pedestrians or cyclists on the road.

Open (government) data are increasingly searchable through regional, national, or European data portals. The acquisition of proprietary data is either done bilaterally or mediated by data marketplaces. For all types of data, the license terms have to be considered for any further data use. In the case of DyMoN, this aspect is of particular relevance since data are integrated and jointly processed. The guideline document “Compendium on Licensing of Geospatial Information” by the United Nations Global Geospatial Information Management (UN-GGIM) is recommended for further reading (United Nations Committee of Experts on Global Geospatial Information Management, 2017).

As outlined in section 2.1, we use the spatial and temporal reference as keys for linking data from various sources and embedding the individual user in the digital representation of the environment (situation). Therefore, acquired data must be georeferenced and time stamped. The latter is particularly relevant for real-time and prognostic data, such as the traffic state, weather, or PT occupancy rate. Data that are relevant for the DyMoN data hub, can have any standardized geospatial format and can be delivered in different ways. Data, which are provided as files or will not be updated regularly, are stored in a central data base. Real-time data are commonly provided via standardized web-interfaces.

The entire DyMoN framework is designed within the paradigm of data minimisation. Therefore, no personal data are stored in the data hub, but remain in the client applications. If required, the Data Hub can be extended to store any user-generated data while taking actions to account to legal regulations and agreements that protect data privacy. Technical details on how requests are processed, and situation-aware nudges are delivered are discussed in more detail below.

3.3 Syntactic interoperability

Situation-aware nudging requires a definition of a situational context specific to each user. Situational context can be described by multidimensional factors of surrounding environment, as well as depending on user’s personal preferences. We use the spatial and temporal reference key for linking situational factors defined in nudging ontologies.

- **Spatial reference key** is user's current, home, and work point locations, coded as geographic coordinate tuple – "geometry" attribute
- **Temporal reference key** is a timestamp of a nudge web-request, in other words the time of a nudge notification sent to a user – "date_time" attribute

In this study, various datasets represent phenomena in space-time continuum. For example, traffic is a spatially and temporarily explicit phenomenon, thus both location and timestamp are used in linking traffic state dataset with user information to check if there are traffic jams in the proximity of a user. For some datasets only spatial dimension is relevant. For example, nudging ontologies use bikeability data that are static from temporal perspective, but vary over space. Hence, such data are integrated based on their location values.

An example of how datasets are joined based on their key references to compute the ruleset of a nudge is given in Figure 4. In this example, four datasets are considered: weather, bikeability network, traffic state, and user information. The arrows show syntactic interoperability of dataset attributes for join relations. First, weather and traffic state observations are filtered based on date_time attribute against the date_time attribute from the user information. This is a use case example of a temporal reference key. Next, the closest weather station is selected based on proximity to the user's location, a use case example of the spatial reference key. As a result of these two joins, situational context regarding weather can be estimated for this specific user. Measurements of the selected stations are aggregated to daily means and are compared with the thresholds for temperature, precipitation, glaze, and wind speed. To calculate further context, a route between user's home and work locations is calculated over the bikeability network. The mean bikeability index of the route is compared with the threshold. In order to check the situation about car traffic in proximity of the user, first, the buffer is calculated around the user's location. Second, network segments with car traffic are filtered by overlapping with the buffer. Third, traffic state of each segment is compared against the thresholds of the ruleset. If the situational context of the user matches with all the nudging conditions, the nudge can be sent to the user.

Figure 4 Interoperability chart of datasets

4 Software architecture

The DyMoN framework consists of three interconnected parts: Data Hub, DyMoN API, and dashboard. The Data Hub stores and calculates data layers and nudges, the DyMoN API schedules nudges and provides secure communication with any external citizens' application, and lastly the dashboard visualizes mobility-related data to citizens and city managers. Any mobile application with the notification system can adapt the DyMoN framework and receive nudges from the DyMoN API that can be forwarded to its users. Possible adjustment steps include data acquisition and threshold adaptations for the area of interest. Presented framework is prepared for Salzburg city.

The software architecture and general processing workflows are visualized in Figure 5. Two main workflows can be distinguished: nudging in the citizens' application and data visualization in the dashboard. The first workflow starts in the DyMoN API by requesting user information from the citizen's app according to the pre-defined schedule. Thus, the DyMoN API controls the time and frequency of nudges per user. Using this information, the DyMoN API generates separate nudge requests per user to the Data Hub. The Data Hub interprets a request per user, calculates a nudge and sends it back to the DyMoN API. In the following processing step, the DyMoN API sends nudge information to the citizens' application. Finally, the citizens' application sends nudge notifications to users.

The second workflow starts in the dashboard, which requests data layers from the DyMoN API. The DyMoN API forwards these requests to the Data Hub, which calculates data layers and sends them back to the DyMoN API. Then, the DyMoN API sends data layer information back to the dashboard.

Figure 5 Software architecture and processing workflow

4.1 Data Hub

The Data Hub has three functions:

- Storage location for data and nudges
- Nudge calculation per user
- Data layers calculation

Its physical location is implemented on a separate server in a PostgreSQL database called “data_hub”. There are two schemas: “data_repository” and “nudge_repository” to store data tables and nudges respectively.

The access to the database is secured via the password authentication and is made available to the internal web server called GeoServer. The GeoServer is an intermediate communication layer that provides access to nudges and data layers from the Data Hub to the DyMoN API. When a web-request is sent by the DyMoN API, the GeoServer interprets it and calls a PostgreSQL function with user parameters from its SQL view. Next, functions are executed directly within the database. Then, the GeoServer sends back an output to the DyMoN API.

Functions:

- `get_nudge(parameters)`
 - calculates a nudge per user following nudge rulesets
 - parameters: `user_group`, `mode_preference`, `date_time`, `location`, `home_location`, `work_location`, `nudge_ids`
- `get_data(parameters)`

- calculates data layers
- parameters: are going to be specified separately per each data layer during the implementation of the dashboard

4.1.1 Data repository

Data repository consists of data tables listed in Table 8. They are datasets required for the calculation of data layers and situation-aware nudges. The composition of attribute fields is given in Table 9, which describes attributes per dataset and identify their data types. The important linking keys for calculating context are given by attributes “date_time” in “YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss” format and “geometry”. Geometry can be of vector or raster topological types: Point, LineString, Polygon, and raster. All geometries are projected in the coordinate reference system WGS 84 / UTM zone 33N (EPSG:32633) and stored in the Well-Known Binary (WKB) format.

Table 8 Input data

Input data	Description
weather	Hourly forecast of temperature, precipitation, wind speed, and sunshine
environment	20-min measurements of temperature and noise by stationary sensors in a test area (field study extent)
noise	Day-evening and night noise indices on roads, railways, flight noise, industry noise
air_quality	Measurements of NO2, PM10, SO2, CO, O3 for the latest 24 h
public_transport	Timetables of departures and arrival times and passenger occupancy at public transport stops
mobility_survey	Travel diaries with trip information
traffic_situation	Traffic state derived from floating car data
bicycle_traffic	Traffic volume from GPS trajectories of bicyclists
bicycle_counts	Traffic volume of bicyclists at counting stations per 15 min
traffic_events	Congestion, troubles, construction sites, and events
bicycle_traffic_events	Bicycle infrastructure with temporal construction sites
public_transport_quality	Public transport accessibility
public_transport_stops	Public transport categories based on frequencies of departures
car_parking	Off-street parking points of interest - public commercial parking garages and park & ride facilities and their occupancy
bicycle_facility	Bicycle parking facilities, e-bike charging stations, bike sharing stations
walkability_network	Network characterized by walkability, greenery, and pleasantness indices for walking trips

bikeability_network	Network characterized by bikeability, greenery, and safety indices for bicycling trips
trip_distances	Reasonable trip distances by mode

Table 9 Data models of data repository datasets

Dataset	Attribute	Data type	Description
weather	date_time	timestamp	timestamp without time zone, in YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss
	geometry	geometry(point)	location of a measurement station
	temperature	integer	air temperature at 2 m, in C°
	precipitation	double precision	precipitation, in mm/h
	wind	double precision	wind speed at 10 m, in m/s
	sunshine	integer	sunshine duration, in h/day
environment	date_time	timestamp	timestamp without time zone, in YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss
	geometry	geometry(point)	location of a sensor box
	temperature	integer	air temperature, in C°
	noise	double precision	noise level, in dB
noise	date_time	timestamp	timestamp without time zone, in YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss
	geometry	raster	10 m ² raster cell
	noise	double precision	noise level in dB
air_quality	date_time	timestamp	timestamp without time zone, in YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss
	geometry	geometry(point)	location of a measurement station
	no2	double precision	Nitrogen dioxide, in µg/m ³
	pm10	double precision	Particulate matter, in µg/m ³
	so2	double precision	Sulphur dioxide, in µg/m ³
	co	double precision	Carbon monoxide, in mg/m ³
	o3	double precision	Ozone, in µg/m ³
public_transport	date_time	timestamp	time of departure, timestamp without time zone, in YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss
	geometry	geometry(point)	location of a stop

	line_id	integer	id of a public transport line
	line_name	text	line name
	direction	text	line direction
	route_id	integer	route id of a line
	route_stop_id	integer	stop id along a route
	stop_id	text	id of a public transport stop
	stop_name	text	stop name
	passenger_occupancy	double precision	occupancy rate, in %
mobility_survey	date_time	timestamp	date and time of a trip, timestamp without time zone, in YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss
	geom_start	geometry (polygon)	municipality location where a trip starts
	geom_end	geometry (polygon)	municipality location where a trip ends
	municipality_start	integer	municipality id where a trip starts
	municipality_end	integer	municipality id where a trip ends
	trip_id	integer	trip id
	person_id	integer	person id
	household_id	integer	household id of a person
	trip_purpose_start	text	trip purpose at starting location
	trip_purpose_end	text	trip purpose at destination location
	mode	text	transport mode
	distance	double precision	trip distance, in km
traffic_state	date_time	timestamp	timestamp without time zone, in YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss
	geometry	geometry (linestring)	street segment location
	los	text	level of service based on vehicle speed from floating cars
	traffic_state	text	traffic state: heavy, congested, and free flow
bicycle_traffic	date_time	timestamp	time of single point measurement along trajectory, timestamp

			without time zone, in YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss
	geometry	geometry(point)	location of a person
	track_id	integer	trajectory id
	point_id	integer	point id along a trajectory
bicycle_counts	date_time	timestamp	timestamp without time zone, in YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss
	geometry	geometry(point)	location of a counting station
	site_id	text	counting station id
	channel_id	text	direction id per station
	direction	text	direction of registered traverses
	counts	integer	number of bicyclists per 15 min
traffic_events	date_time	timestamp	creation date, timestamp without time zone, in YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss
	geometry	geometry(point)	location of event
	message_id	integer	message id
	message_text	text	text of a message
	event	text	type of traffic event
	status	text	current status
	street_name	text	street name where an event occurs
	street_start	text	street where an event starts
	street_end	text	street where an event ends
	direction	text	direction of event
	valid_start	timestamp	validity start date, timestamp without time zone, in YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss
	valid_end	timestamp	validity end date, timestamp without time zone, in YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss
public_transport_quality	geometry	geometry (polygon)	polygon cells of 100 m ²
	quality_class	text	public transport quality class
	distance	integer	distance to public transport stops, in m

public_transport_stops	geometry	geometry(point)	location of a public transport stop
	category	text	Category by departare frequency interval
	departure_frequency	integer	Departure frequency interval, in min
car_parking	date_time	timestamp	timestamp without time zone, in YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss
	geometry	geometry(point)	location of a parking facility
	occupancy_rate	double precision	partly current utilization, in %
	opening hours	text	opening hours
	price	integer	prices
	payment_options	text	payment options
	contacts	text	operator information and contact possibility
bicycle_facility	geometry	geometry(point)	location of a bicycle facility
	type	text	Type of a bicycle facility
bicycle_traffic_events	date_time	timestamp	Time of creation, timestamp without time zone, in YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss
	geometry	geometry(point)	location of a construction
	valid_start	timestamp	validity start date, timestamp without time zone, in YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss
	valid_end	timestamp	validity end date, timestamp without time zone, in YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss
walkability_network	geometry	geometry (linestring)	location of a network link
	walkability	double precision	walkability index
	green_walkway_ind	double precision	walkability index weighted by green ratio
	beautiful_walkway_ind	double precision	walkability index weighted by pleasantness
walkability_raster	geometry	raster	raster cell of 50 m ²
	walkability	double precision	mean walkability index in the proximity of 400 m

	green_walkway_ind	double precision	mean walkability index weighted by green ratio in the proximity of 400 m
	beautiful_walkway_ind	double precision	mean walkability index weighted by pleasantness in the proximity of 400 m
bikeability_network	geometry	geometry (linestring)	location of a network link
	bikeability	double precision	bikeability index
	green_bicycle_way_ind	double precision	bikeability index weighted by green ratio
	safe_bicycle_way_ind	double precision	bikeability index weighted by safety
bikeability_raster	geometry	raster	raster cell of 50 m ²
	bikeability	double precision	mean bikeability index in the proximity of 400 m
	green_bicycle_way_ind	double precision	mean bikeability index weighted by green ratio in the proximity of 400 m
	safe_bicycle_way_ind	double precision	mean bikeability index weighted by safety in the proximity of 400 m

4.1.2 Nudge repository

Nudge repository consists of one table “nudges”. Its data model is described in Table 10. This table defines the input for nudge rulesets. Each nudge is characterized by mode, user group (intervention/control), timeframe, and specific threshold for situational context of a user. The function “get_nudge()” goes through each nudge and checks its threshold against user information and current environmental situation.

Table 10 Data model of the “nudges” table

Attribute	Data type	Description	Possible values
nudge_id	unique identifier	integer	
nudge_title	short title of a nudge notification	text	
nudge_text	nudge notification message in german	text	
nudge_text_eng	nudge notification message in english	text	

mode	target transport mode	text	walking, bicycling, public transport
user_group	type of user group in a test study	text array	intervention, control
weekdays	scheduled day of week	text array	Monday, Tuesday...
time_start	scheduled start time	timestamp	hh:mm:ss
time_end	scheduled end time	timestamp	hh:mm:ss
location_start	assumed starting point for situation assessment	text	home, current, work
location_end	assumed destination point for situation assessment	text	home, current, work, none
situational_factors	situation description via spatio-temporal conditions of an environment	text	
temporal_filter	timeframe of situation (forecast for current day/next day)	text	current day, next day
temperature	temperature type	text	moderate, positive
precipitation	presence of rainfall	text	rainfall, no rainfall
precipitation_window	presence of rainfall at a specific period	text	no rainfall next hour
glaze	presence of glaze	text	no glaze
wind	presence of wind	text	no strong winds
sunshine	presence of sunshine	text	sunshine
walkability	quality of network regarding pedestrian comfort and safety	text	high
bikeability	quality of network regarding cyclist comfort and safety	text	high
trip_distance	distance to destination by mode	text	reasonable
pt_proximity	presence of public transport stop	text	present
pt_departure_frequency	frequency of departures per 15 min at transport stops	text	high

pt_occupancy	occupancy rate in % at transport stops	text	low
traffic_state	traffic state	text	congested
car_parking_availability	car parking availability in %	text	low
green_bicycle_way	presence of areas with green spaces, like parks and forests along a bicycle way	text	present
green_walkway	presence of areas with green spaces, like parks and forests along a walkway	text	present
beautiful_walkway	presence of walkways with green and water spaces around	text	present
safe_bicycle_way	presence of safe bicycle lanes	text	present

4.1.3 API

The GeoServer web server plays a role of an API for accessing data and nudges by the DyMoN API, which is the API for external applications. Several SQL views are defined in the GeoServer workspace for DyMoN framework. These SQL views can access the PostgreSQL database and execute queries and functions on data tables stored in the database.

Instructions to the API:

- GeoServer API endpoint: <https://mobilitylab.geo.sbg.ac.at/geoserver/dymon/>
- Authentication: user login/password
- Requests: GetFeature
- Response format: JSON

There are two GET request examples that the GeoServer can receive and interpret:

Nudge request:

- URL: https://mobilitylab.geo.sbg.ac.at/geoserver/dymon/wfs?version=2.0.0&request=GetFeature&typeName=dymon:nudges&outputFormat=application/json&viewparams=user_type:intervention;mode_preference:bicycle;time:2022-11-02T09:59:28.071Z;location:0101000020E61000008351499D801;home_location:0101000020E61000008351499D801;work_location:0101000020E6100000DAFF006BD5162;nudge_ids:2,63
- Version: 2.0.0
- Request: GetFeature
- Output format: JSON
- Parameters: user_group, mode_preference, time, location, home_location, work_location, nudge_ids
- Response: nudge_id, nudge_title, nudge_text

Data layer request:

- URL: https://mobilitylab.geo.sbg.ac.at/geoserver/dymon/wfs?version=2.0.0&request=GetFeature&typeName=dymon:%20bikeability_network&styles=outputFormat=application/json&viewparams=dataset:bikeability_network;bbox:0101000020040000000000;time:2022-11-02T09:59:28.071Z;measurement_unit:null
- Version: 2.0.0
- Request: GetFeature
- Output format: GeoJSON
- Parameters: dataset, bbox (spatial bounding box), time, measurement_unit

4.2 DyMoN API

The DyMoN API is responsible for the communication between all parties. It is a services-based orchestration of different docker modules, all written in Python. They all communicate in an Event-Driven-Architectural style. The process starts with the scheduler service. Since the service requests all the data it needs and then receives it as an answer there are no public endpoints needed.

The service starts 3 times a day, as shown in the table below. Two times the service sends the nudges as early as possible in a given time frame and once it sends the nudges at a random time stamp in a given time frame. The time stamp is randomly selected just once for all nudges, so also in the scenario they all are going to be sent together. Whether a nudge is really sent at the scheduled times depends on whether a nudge matches the filters (see chapter [2.2](#)). Most nudges are related to morning and evening times, i.e. in most cases nudges are only sent in the morning and evening and on Friday afternoons.

Table 11 Scheduling times

time range name	Time range	Time when nudge is sent
morning	06:00-08:00	as early as possible within time range
afternoon	12:00-15:00	at random timestamp within time range
evening	20:00-22:00	as early as possible within time range

Get User request:

The service requests the current list of all active users and the necessary information.

- URL: Endpoint at Pandocs
- Request: GET
- Response:

```

{
  "timestamp": "2022-09-21 06:00:00",
  "users": [
    {
      "temporaryUserId": "2f29a587-4d58-42aa-9e3e-7eb1abaaa215",
      "group": "control",
      "modePreference": "bicycle",
      "currentLocation": {
        "latitude": 12.234,
        "longitude": 42.123123
      },
      "homeLocation": {
        "latitude": 12.675,
        "longitude": 42.32456
      }
    },
    {
      "temporaryUserId": "b9195196-9309-44a3-a063-3928476447f2",
      "group": "intervention",
      "modePreference": "walk",
      "currentLocation": {
        "latitude": 12.768,
        "longitude": 42.12635
      },
      "homeLocation": {
        "latitude": 12.982,
        "longitude": 42.23363
      }
    }
  ]
}

```

Send nudges request:

The service sends a list of the associated nudges from the nudge repository

- URL: Endpoint at Pandocs
- Request: POST
- Body:

```

{
  "nudges": [
    {
      "temporaryUserId": "2f29a587-4d58-42aa-9e3e-7eb1abaaa215",
      "nudgeId": 12,
      "nudgeText": "Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing."
    },
    {
      "temporaryUserId": "b9195196-9309-44a3-a063-3928476447f2",
      "nudgeId": 67,
      "nudgeText": "Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud."
    }
  ]
}

```

- Response: 201 - created

Furthermore, the DyMoN API provides the Dashboard with all the necessary information. This will be done via REST endpoints and POST requests. To be able to fulfill this task, the DyMoN API will store the data it receives from the Aspern sensor boxes in its own database. It will offer an endpoint where it will receive data from the boxes every 20 minutes.

Figure 5: DyMoN API Component-Diagram

5 End clients

5.1 Citizens' mobile application

Citizens' mobile application is an end-client application that interacts with citizen users and sends them nudges. It does so by adapting the DyMoN framework in their pipeline. There are a few functional requirements that the mobile application should comprise of:

- Collection and storage of user profiles
- Tracking users' current/last location
- Sending user information as a response to the DyMoN API. User information should include temporary user id (stored and updated every day), group (control/intervention), mode preference, current time, current/last recorded location, home location, work location
- Translation of the responses from DyMoN API into challenges
- Provision of links to Lime surveys (field study only)
- Storage of user statistics about their interaction with challenges (field study only)

Provision of links to Lime surveys and the storage of user statistics is provided only for the field study purposes and are not essential for the DyMoN framework operability. Pandocs application is used for the field study.

5.2 Dashboard

The DyMoN dashboard addresses citizens as well as city or location managers and presents current relevant data related to sustainable mobility in the field study area/city. It will be implemented by using the React framework. Its aim is to raise awareness about current conditions and opportunities for sustainable mobility. There are two different application areas for the DyMoN dashboard. As a **non-interactive dashboard**, it is displayed on a

screen in the entrance area of the test location. It updates automatically and provides easy to grasp information about sustainable mobility in the test location and its surroundings, addressing people passing by (e.g., employees working at the test location). As an **interactive dashboard** to be used on desktop or mobile, it offers additional information and allows users to explore the respective data. It addresses field study participants, people related to the test location or other interested persons, who would like to learn more about current sustainable mobility opportunities in the city.

The dashboard features a map, tiles with different key performance indicators (KPIs), a list with the next public transport departures and a motivational (non-situation-aware) nudge text. In the non-interactive dashboard, the map is centred and zoomed to the test area and all data shown refers to the surroundings of the test location. In the interactive dashboard, the KPIs refer to the city in general or also to the test location, in case there is no other data (sensor boxes). The following tables show the available data variables in the different dashboard elements.

Table 12 Map layers in the non-interactive and interactive dashboard

Category	Data variable	Non-interactive dashboard	Interactive dashboard
environment	location of environment sensor boxes	✓	✓
	location of air quality measurement stations	only the ones around test area	✓
events	current construction sites	only the ones around test area	✓
	location of traffic events	only the ones around test area	✓
	location of bicycle traffic events	only the ones around test area	✓
public transport	public transport stop locations	only the ones around test area	✓
	public transport quality class (polygons)	-	✓
cycling	location of bicycle counting stations	only the ones around test area	✓
	location of bicycle facilities	only the ones around test area	✓
	bikeability raster	-	✓
	greenery-weighted bikeability raster	-	✓
	safety-weighted bikeability raster	-	✓
walking	walkability raster	-	✓
	greenery-weighted walkability raster	-	✓
	pleasantness-weighted walkability raster	-	✓

Table 13 List element in the non-interactive and interactive dashboard

Data variable	Description	Non-interactive dashboard	Interactive dashboard
Next PT departures	List with departures (stop name, line name, direction, time of departure, passenger occupancy), ordered by time of departure	For the stops around the test area	For user-selected stops

Table 14 Key performance indicators in the dashboard

Data variable	Metric	Reference value
Bicycle traffic volume	Count of bicycle traverses at station within the last hour	Average count of bicycle traverses at the station per hour at the same hour of the day on the same weekday within the last 30 days (show deviation from reference value)
Noise	Current noise level in dB, measured at sensor box	Average noise level at the same hour of the day on the same weekday in the last 30 days (show deviation from reference value)
Temperature	Current air temperature in °C, measured at sensor box	Average temperature at the same hour of the day in the last 7 days (show deviation from reference value)
Air pollution (PM10)	Daily average PM10 level in µg/m ³ for the previous day	Official pollution limit value (50 µg/m ³) (show textual air quality evaluation level)
Field study participants	Number of active participants in field study today	Average number of active participants in the field study within the last 7 days (show deviation from reference value)

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